

CHARACTERISTICS OF A NEW METHOD FOR PROCESSING OF PREFORMED GLASS MAT REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

Lars A. Berglund & Mats L. Ericson
Linköping Institute of Technology
Dept of Mechanical Engineering
S-581 83 Linköping, Sweden

ABSTRACT

A method is presented for the fabrication of a GMT preform. Fiber roving is cut and mixed with a thermoplastic powder and sprayed onto a porous net to build a preform. The preform is then heated by a gas flow. The hot preform is moved to a press and molded into a component by hot stamping. The processing of preformed GMT offers advantages such as lower material cost and the possibility to tailor the material composition. The mechanical properties of preformed GMT are similar to the properties of conventional GMT although the data show large scatter. The reason is that the microstructures are inhomogeneous. The technology of preformed GMT makes it possible to study the effect of improved material homogeneity on material properties.

KEYWORDS: GMT; Preform; Glass fiber/ polypropylene; Tensile strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass mat reinforced thermoplastics, GMT, are used extensively in the automotive industry. Polypropylene is often chosen as matrix due to its low cost and high toughness. The GMT material is delivered to the molder as semi-finished sheet. The semi-finished material is heated and molded by a rapid hot stamping technique. Material compositions with glass fiber contents ranging from 10 to 25 percent by volume are available. In our laboratory, a new method for GMT processing was recently developed (1). The objective of the present paper is to compare the characteristics of this method and the resulting material with those of the commercially available GMT.

2. METHODS OF GMT PROCESSING

2.1 Conventional GMT processing The actual molding operation during GMT processing is rapid and straight-forward. Semi-finished sheet are cut to the appropriate size, stacked and heated until they soften, usually by means of an infra-red oven. The hot material is rapidly transferred to a press with capability of rapid mold closure. The material is then molded in a matched-die steel mold which is at ambient temperature. A sketch of the set-up is presented in Fig 1.

For manufacture of the semi-finished sheet there are two different approaches (2,3,4). In the most common approach, a glass mat is fed to a belt press together with polymer film and/or molten polymer from a sheet extruder, see Fig 2. The press has heating zones where impregnation of the glass fibers occur and towards the end of the belt press the material is cooled for subsequent cutting.

In the other approach based on paper technology, the reinforcing fibers and polymer powder are mixed in an aqueous slurry, see Fig 3. The mixture is dried and consolidated under heat and pressure. Some manufacturers do not consolidate the material, instead a special heating procedure is used for the molding operation.

2.2 Preformed GMT - a new approach The purpose of our development of a process for fabrication of preformed GMT was to reduce material cost. In the form of powder and fiber roving the material is expected to be cheaper than semi-finished GMT sheet. A detailed description of the process, the equipment and the material is given in (1). The method is inspired by the spray-up procedures used for thermoset composites. Modern developments of resin transfer molding (RTM) include a preforming technique for components of complicated geometry. Here a preform of fiber and a polymeric binder is first fabricated. A porous net is used as mold and chopped glass fiber roving is sprayed onto the net together with a binder dissolved in water. The purpose of the binder is to keep the fibers together in the preform. This preform is then dried and placed in an RTM mold which is closed and the liquid thermoset is injected and cured.

In order to fabricate a GMT preform, we built an apparatus based on a spray gun where the apparatus was intended to cut, mix and spray fiber roving and thermoplastic powder onto a porous net to build a preform. In the next step of the process, the preform is heated by a gas flow so that the polymer becomes soft. The hot preform is moved to the press and molded into a component by hot stamping.

The following experimental processing equipment was designed and built; a preform fabrication apparatus, a heating apparatus for the preform and a modified molding press. The roving from the glass fibre bobbin is cut in a

rotating cutter of a spray gun. The chopped strands are forced into a T-connection and mixed with the thermoplastic powder. An air flow extender accelerates the fiber/powder mixture and forces it through a PVC-tube. The mixture is sprayed onto a porous net to build the preform. The fibers and the powder are kept on the net by application of vacuum. After the preform fabrication, the preform is heated by hot nitrogen gas. The gas is heated by an electric gas heater which also controls the temperature. When the preform has been heated, the next step is the molding operation. We modified a laboratory press by using a 50 ton hydraulic cylinder and a 700 bar hydraulic pump in order to obtain the fast mold closure speeds required.

Fig 4 shows how GMT preform fabrication and the subsequent molding of preformed GMT could be accomplished on a commercial scale. The spray-up is performed by a robot and the heating is done in an oven with circulating gas.

3. DISCUSSION

3.1. Processing aspects Stamping of GMT is a rapid process where a total processing time of thirty seconds in the press is not uncommon. Usually there is no need for a trimming operation. The major difference between the actual molding operation of conventional GMT and preformed GMT is the fact that the geometry of preformed GMT approximately follows the contours of the mould. Since the microstructure of the preformed GMT can be chosen to be similar to conventional GMT, this means that more complicated geometries can be molded with preformed GMT.

The primary advantage with the preforming approach is that the material cost is likely to be lowered as compared with the conventional approach. We have used polypropylene powder as obtained from the reactor and glass fiber roving as starting materials. Therefore, there is no need to fabricate a semi-finished sheet which needs storage, transport and reheating. Instead raw materials are only heated once before they become constituents of the final component. An additional advantage is that we can tailor the material composition by the choice of fiber type, fiber length, fiber content, roving bundle size, sizing, degree of dispersion, polymer type and molecular weight distribution.

3.2 Mechanical properties The tensile strength and modulus of different GMT are presented in Table 1. The semi-finished Symalit material is made by the belt press melt impregnation procedure and has looped glass fiber roving reinforcement where the individual fibers are kept together in bundles in the final microstructure. The Ahlström material is made by the process inspired by paper technology and contains chopped fibers where individual fibers are fairly well dispersed. The preformed GMT has a microstructure closer to the Ahlström material but the fibers are bent with a characteristic radius of curvature, approximately 20-40 mm.

From the large differences in microstructure between different types of GMT one would expect some differences in modulus and tensile strength. However, as is apparent from the data on tensile strength versus fiber volume fraction for different materials in Fig 5, there is large experimental scatter in the data.

Regarding the large scatter in the data, other workers have also obtained similar results (5,6,7). In more detailed studies of the mechanical properties of GMT it was concluded that variations in the microstructure have little effect on the average property values (8,9). We also found that the material compositions with high strength also showed the lowest scatter of the data. This leads us to propose that the apparent insensitivity of GMT materials to differences in microstructure may be caused by the inhomogeneity of the materials. The properties are controlled by the inhomogeneity rather than by microstructural details. If the inhomogeneity of the material controls its properties, one possible route to improve the properties of the material is to improve the dispersion of the fibers. Studies on preformed GMT may shed light on the problem of inhomogeneity since the microstructure can be controlled within wide limits.

6. CONCLUSIONS

As compared with conventional GMT, the processing of preformed GMT offer advantages such as lower material cost and the possibility to tailor the material composition. The mechanical properties of preformed GMT are similar to the properties of conventional GMT. However, the measured tensile strength and modulus of both conventional and preformed GMT show large scatter. The reason is that the microstructure of these materials is inhomogeneous with local variations in fiber volume fraction and fiber distribution. The technology of preformed GMT will allow us to conduct studies on the effect of improved material homogeneity on material properties.

REFERENCES

1. M. Ericson and L. Berglund in J. Füller et. al.,ed., Proceedings of the Fourth European Conference on Composites Materials, ECCM-4, Elsevier applied science, London and New York, 1990, pp. 67, 1078.
2. J. Six, 21 Öffentliche Jahrestagung der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Verstärkte Kunststoffe e.V., Mainz November 2-4 1987, pp. 22.1-22.8.
3. P.A. van Damme, Proceedings of the International Conference of Fibre Reinforced Composites, University of Liverpool March 23-25 1988, Plastics and Rubber Institute, London, 1988, pp. 1/1-1/14.

4. D.F. Hiscock and D.M. Bigg, *Polymer Composites*, 10 (3), 145 (1989).
5. V.K. Stokes, *Polymer Composites*, 11 (1), 32 (1990).
6. V.K. Stokes, *Polymer Composites*, 11 (6), (1990).
7. G.D. Tomkinson-Walles, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 1 (1), 94 (1988).
8. M. Ericson and L. Berglund, *Journal of Composites Science and Technology*, to be published.
9. M. Ericson and L. Berglund, Submitted for publication in *Polymer Composites*.

TABLE

Table 1. Tensile strength and creep modulus of GMT materials, measured at approximately 0.5 % strain after 100 seconds at constant load.

Material	Fiber structure	Creep modulus, E _{100s}		Tensile strength, σ _f	
		V _f = 0.1 (GPa)	V _f = 0.2 (GPa)	V _f = 0.1 (MPa)	V _f = 0.2 (MPa)
Preformed	Discrete, 51 mm	4.1	7.2	66	93
Symalit	Looped bundles	3.2	5.9	59	88
Ahlström	Discrete, 12 mm	3.7	6.5	66	95

FIGURES

Figure 1. Schematic of typical set-up for hot stamping of GMT.

Figure 2. The fabrication of semi-finished GMT sheet by melt impregnation. A) thermoplastic resin overlays, B) glass fiber mat, C) extruder, D) thermoplastic resin extrudate, E) double belt laminator, F) heating zone, G) cooling zone, H) finished sheet product.

Figure 3. The fabrication of semi-finished GMT-sheet by approach based on paper technology.

Figure 4. Schematic of GMT preform fabrication and molding. a) powder feeder, b) glass fiber bobbin, c) rotating cutter, d) robot, e) preform, f) preform vacuum machine, g) circulating through-air heater, h) press.

Figure 5. Tensile strength as a function of fiber volume fraction for three different GMT.